

NeRDS
Network Research
Data Support

NETWORK RESEARCH DATA SUPPORT

The year **2025** in figures

RDM Support Desk – # calls 2022 - 2025

RDM Support Desk – calls per faculty 2014 - 2025

Top 5 Support Desk – calls per category 2025

RDM Support Desk – Top 5 Support Desk calls 2023 - 2025

DMP Online - new Data Management Plans created 2020 - 2025

Research Drive vs Yoda – Projects, users and volumes

Projects

Users

Volumes (TB)

Data Storage – UBVU RDM solutions volumes 2022 - 2025

Data Storage – UBVU RDM solutions users 2022 - 2025

Yoda – Projects and volumes per faculty 2024

Research Drive – Volumes and projects per faculty 2025

Open Science FFramework – Total #users per faculty 2022 - 2025

SciStor – Projects, users and volumes 2025

Qualtrics – users per faculty 2022-2024

Qualtrics – surveys per faculty 2022 - 2025

ELN solution SciSure – usage 2025

Faculty	Labs	Research groups	Licences	Volumes
BETA	12	16	221	79
FGB	2	3	86	11
ACTA	4	4	20	1

Open Science & RDM Training 2022 - 2025

RDM training - #courses

RDM training - #participants

DMP course – Participants per faculty 2024 - 2025

NeRDS

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- RDM information: rdm.vu.nl
- RDM support calls: services.vu.nl
- RDM support desk: rdm@vu.nl
- NeRDS Roadmap 2025-2030: <https://zenodo.org/records/18628804>

For further information about the Network Research Data Support or the RDM Monitor, contact Marcel Ras (Coordinator Network Research Data Support), m.j.m.ras@vu.nl